

EUCLID RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Ikuku**FIRST NAME:** Clara**PROGRAM CODE:** DCCS**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

List your seven key concepts with the page number in-text (then bold these terms in your RP (samples below):

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. Response Paper (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)
4. Grammarly, Qesta and Jstor (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)
5. Common Errors EUCLID 2019, 6-7)
6. Using RP template (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
7. RP and Major Papers (EUCLID 2019, 49-55)

ESSENTIAL CONCEPTS IN ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

In my 20 years of professional practice as a Geologist and Petroleum Engineer, I have written many technical reports and documentation that applied either the Turabian in-text reference styles in addition to the footnote references. Often the English and American writing styles were used together within the same document. In the Oil and Gas environment, report writing styles did not follow the academic styles explained in this course. Those types of documents all share a common attribute: a conceptual idea statement, creation of a beginning and an end of deliverable, political and environmental constraints affecting the deliverable, all reported within natural domains of expertise. Often there are catalogs of standard auto-generated reports available that are used and edited appropriately with project-specific details. These report guidelines along technical discipline-specific paths were easy to follow for someone who is not an English native like me. For industry technical papers, like the Society of Petroleum Engineers (SPE), guidelines are provided on how reports are titled, how the abstract is constructed, how the statement of theory and definitions is presented, described, and concluded. For grammar and style, the SPE guideline allows both the British and American styles within the same report. According to the SPE guideline, “Use of either British or American spelling or grammar is acceptable” (spe.org, Preparing Your Paper). Coming from such a

background, I am excited to see how this response paper activity would change my writing perspective.

2) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is considered academic dishonesty, a breach of ethics, and compromised integrity (Selemani, Chawinga, and Dube 2018, 24-25). Plagiarism was extensively discussed in the opening chapter of the ACA-401D period one (1) of the course pack. I understand EUCLID, like other reputable institutions of higher learning, eschews plagiarism as a plague in any academic community. In the paragraph stressing the stance of the college on plagiarism, it was stated that “ EUCLID expects absolute compliance of the strict copyright regulations including acceptable international fair use guidelines, just as it expects full compliance with strict plagiarism and academic integrity guidelines” (EUCLID 2019, 2).

Plagiarism is not in itself a crime but can constitute copyright infringement. It is my opinion that plagiarism poses an academic menace that should be phased out of the academic community. The World Association of Medical Editors (WAME) defines plagiarism as “ the use of others’ published and unpublished ideas or words (or other intellectual property) without attribution or permission and presenting them as new and original rather than derived from an existing source” (World Association of Medical Editors 2016, 23).

Researchers also found that despite students reporting that they had a conceptual understanding of plagiarism, the majority of them reported that they had intentionally and unintentionally committed plagiarism, mainly due to pressure for good grades (86.7%), laziness, and poor time management (84.9%), and lack of good academic writing skills (84.9%).(Selemani, Chawinga, and Dube 2018, 61-69). There are four different types of plagiarism, namely, verbatim, mosaic, paraphrasing, and self-plagiarism (Indian 2016, 14). None of those are acceptable, and students should be careful not to fall victim to them.

However, a consensus has been reached in the literature that educating students on good academic writing skills and raising awareness on the negative effects of plagiarism are the best strategies to deal with plagiarism (Leask, Macdonald, Carroll, Pecorari and Walker 2018, 51-53).

3) RESPONSE PAPER(RP)

The idea of Euclid’s response paper (RP) is new but fascinating. It reminds me of my initial struggles in learning the tenets of the American Psychological Association writing during my recent master’s program. I do imagine that this doctoral program demanding more of my writing prowess could create an initial struggle in terms of its strict adherence to course requirements. Indeed, completing a course or module and

obtaining credits towards degree completion requires a sustained and intense effort (EUCLID 2019, 1).

A response paper (RP) is a short (2.5-5 pages) assignment that must be written using the most recent EUCLID response paper template (EUCLID 2019, 2-4). I could see lots of differences between the Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association (APA) format of writing and the Turabian style. For instance, while APA allows double spacing, the Turabian style could only be single-spaced with a different parenthetical (in-text) referencing. Notwithstanding, it is imperative that unless otherwise specified, EUCLID expects students to use the Turabian rule of style (EUCLID 2019, 2-3).

Furthermore, it is interesting to learn that when no specific question is asked, a generic or open response paper is expected (EUCLID 2019, 2). In terms of general organization or formatting of a response paper, its outlines feature seven major headings such as introduction, first, second, third, fourth, fifth point discussion, conclusion, and references. This is very similar to the APA format. However, due to the brevity of the response paper, the use of sub-headings in the template could be skipped. This is similar to the APA format where writers use at least two subheadings for each section and subsection or use none. My understanding of APA format eases the pressure of writing this response paper to suit the current writing guidelines in ACA-401D.

Another interesting expectation of students while writing a response paper is that they make it as interactive and personal as possible such that students could demonstrate and reflect in a manner that suggests they have made the learning their own. This is because the purpose of a response paper is not to cut and paste various paragraphs from the materials, which would constitute plagiarism and result in academic penalties (EUCLID 2019, 4).

4) GRAMMARLY, QUESTIA, AND JSTOR

EUCLID's penchant for flawless and original papers is proven in their making additional proof-reading platforms available to students. Before I enrolled for this doctorate program, I was only aware of a few plagiarism-testing platforms such as www.ithenticate.com, www.turnitin.com, www.plagiarism.org as a way of avoiding plagiarism violations. I am excited I am now provided an avalanche of platforms such as Grammarly, Questia, and Jstor to test originality and improve the quality of writings beyond what I used to know. It is gratifying to realize that EUCLIDS provides additional support to students towards improving their writing skills and enabling them to conduct plagiarism assessment (EUCLID 2019, 3)

I consider it a novelty that EUCLID provided a Grammarly premium subscription for free, although I never received the Grammarly voucher I requested. The use of Grammarly will undoubtedly leave every student with no excuse to turning in near-flawless or flawless writing tasks.

5) USING THE RP TEMPLATE

EUCLID provides a selection of sample response papers which are very useful to carefully analyze before launching into the writing process for the first response paper (EUCLID 2019, 5). This is highly commendable as this helps to provide a useful framework for writing appropriately and communicate the expectations of the instructor. This will also reduce the amount of questions students ask instructors as they embark on their assignments. I also gathered from the information contained in the ACA-401D course pack that the use of the EUCLID RP template is mandatory due to the special features that are imbibed in it. It was stated that the template provides a standardized and uniform format for the main components of the word documents (EUCLID 2019, 5).

As a way of keeping up with regular changes applied to the RP template, students are expected to keep up with changes as they are updated every year. Also, RP documents are expected to be saved in a specific way while using this template, using a canonical name. The format of saving the document should reflect the student's name, course abbreviation, assignment, and the period e.g., Clara Ikuku DCCS ACA-401D RP1.

In terms of common mistakes students make, the ACA-401D course materials identified errors or pitfalls students have to be aware of. A few of them include Zotero errors (due to improper entries and document conversion) and grammar-related errors. Common mistakes such as adding blank lines, the use of contractions, placing a period at the end of a title or subheading, or even having two (2) periods in a single sentence were discussed and considered prohibited.

Another vital aspect of RP writing is the creation of quizzes by students. I learned from the ACA-401D course pack that either at the end of period five or period six, upon completion of the five response papers, the next assignment will be to create a quiz (EUCLID 2019, 6). The school expects students to assume the role of a professor at this point, think thoroughly about the entire content and coverage of material and generate appropriate questions that could test the understanding of a student as though they were the instructor.

The quiz format is usually ten (10) questions drawn from different aspects of the material to reflect students' mastery. Moreover, questions generated are expected to be appropriately difficult, somewhat commensurate to the level of the program, covering important aspects of the material such as events, institution, individual and not details that drift attention from the focus of the course.

6) RP AND MAJOR PAPERS

The ACA-401D course pack carefully compared the features of response papers (RPs) with those of major papers (MPs). Their differences and similarities were also highlighted. For instance, they are similar in that both papers have approved EUCLID

templates. However, major papers (MPs) are quite different from response papers, notable because they are meant to be very academic and, therefore, impersonal, whereas response papers are by nature more interactive and therefore conversational (EUCLID 2019, 7). Other differences identified between the two (2) papers are: MPs are double-spaced while RPs are single-spaced. MPs have footnote referencing, while RP has in-text referencing. RP is typically between two and a half (2.5) and five (5) pages, while MPs are between fourteen (14) and eighteen (18) pages. While MPs focus on specific topics from a broad spectrum of knowledge gained throughout the course, RP is focused on the general concepts of the material in focus.

Additionally, EUCLID insists on the use of headings in MPs which explains why it is longer than RP. This key feature is substantiated by a statement contained in the ACA-401D course pack that even though it is a commonplace at other institutions to see fairly long major papers taking the form of running text without headings, this is unacceptable at EUCLID (EUCLID 2019, 7). The MPs also contain several running citations formatted in quote style while the body is formatted in normal style.

7) CONCLUSION

My first experience as it is no verbiage to conclude that this session has provided me a suitable tutelage towards successful completion of my DCCS, a doctoral degree in Climate and Sustainability. With the availability of the ACA-401D course pack, I became literarily 'baptized' into the unique world of EUCLID's academic writing. The Turabian style of writing has taken center stage of my learning at the start of this doctoral program, and it has increased my level of awareness and galvanized me against possible errors in future tasks.

Stretching me from my prior knowledge of APA academic writing style, which used to be the epitome of my academic writing style or format, has given way to the Turabian style as a consequence of my interaction with the ACA-401D course pack. I realized the Turabian style (Eighth Edition), which is the EUCLID's preferred and recommended style of writing, proved to be of peculiar requirements in the form of in-text citation, referencing, and formatting (Turabian 2013, 304).

It was fun learning new rules of formatting, plagiarism, response paper specifications, the seven concepts of writing a response, and major papers. These items were of immense importance towards understanding the expectations of the instructor.

Penultimately, the ACA-401D course pack afforded me increased awareness about plagiarism and ethical issues among students. I understand it is important that individuals stay honest in their work and should not violate copyright laws. I will keep track of the sources consulted during research, paraphrase or quote from sources (and add my ideas), credit the original author in an in-text citation and reference list, and use a plagiarism checker before submitting work.

Finally, I feel confident that my active participation in this program will significantly improve my ability to deliver scholarly-written papers and also help in delivering more professional technical papers.

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